

QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Jadigerova Gulnaz Maratovna

Assistant teacher at the Department of General Pedagogy and Psychology, Faculty of Primary Education. Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz.

The Republic of Uzbekistan. Nukus city.

Annotation: In the modern system of higher education, much attention is paid to quality, which ensures the competitiveness of an educational institution in the educational services market through the training of qualified specialists that meet the requirements of international standards. At the bottom of every work lies knowledge and experience. A person comes into the world, and during his life he learns only science and craft. During this period, a person experiences the process of education. He receives the initial education in the family, which is the pillar of the society, over time, he continues to kindergarten, school, higher education and so on. In this article What is the role of education in our lives, how is the name of the year chosen by our president, the quality of education provided by teachers and coaches during the education process, and how much the state pays attention to the quality of education. is covered comprehensively.

Key words: innovation, trend, accreditation, monitoring, certification.

The quality of education is the condition of the quality of society's life and its prosperity. There is probably no one who disagrees with the opinion that improving the quality of education should be better than it is now. Modern life requires wider

and deeper knowledge and therefore better education. Economic changes in the country force state universities to engage in marketing research along with traditional activities, to improve financial management, to implement strategic planning of their development, and to expand the scope of additional professional education.

The quality of education as a narrow concept is the direct result of the educational process, depending on the level of qualification of pedagogical personnel, the organization of the educational and methodological process, the state of the material and technical base, intellectual potential. In addition to the quality of education, the demand for graduates of an educational institution, their success, employers' perception of graduates including professional evaluation, university-industry relations, absence or presence of criticism.

The analysis of the modern legal foundations of education shows that the need to ensure the quality of education is not a temporary reform of the Ministry of Education and Science, but a long-term state policy. Understanding the content of the concept and the conditions for providing quality education has undergone a long evolution. The meaning of the concept of "quality of education" in official documents has changed and expanded. Accordingly, following these trends in the regulatory and legal framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the requirements for higher education institutions have also changed. If we refer to the words of the President, which are regularly heard in his addresses about the idea of the quality of education, the issues of its control and provision, we can clearly see the main stages of this process.

The concept of accreditation in the field of education is inextricably linked with the concept of quality: accreditation is the official recognition by authorized bodies of

teaching in a certain educational program, a certain university, etc., that meets the established quality standards.

Accreditation is a central tool for ensuring important reform processes in European higher education systems. Like assessment, accreditation serves to measure the quality of new degree programs and monitor existing ones. Accreditation, that is, certification of the degree program, is carried out after checking the minimum standards of content and specialization, the professional suitability of the given degree, the consistency and harmony of the general concept of the degree program. The educational program is accredited for a certain period of time, taking into account the transparency of the evaluation procedures. The professional review process by experts is managed by agencies, which also regularly review through external evaluation. In the context of the growth of the educational services provided by the network of educational providers, the problem of the quality of education provided by them remains extremely urgent.

Accreditation is not a relatively new phenomenon in the European educational culture. The state accreditation of the higher education institution came into force in 1992. This is a mechanism for the state to guarantee the quality of education for all citizens and to determine the status of the state.

The state recognition procedure consists of three stages:

- licensing - assessment of the compliance of educational activity conditions with state requirements for classrooms, laboratory equipment, teaching staff, educational literature;
- attestation - evaluation of the compliance of the content, level and quality of graduate training with the requirements of the state educational standard;

- accreditation - types of university (higher educational institution) and types (institute, academy, university) to determine the status of state accreditation (confirmation for the next term).

The university has the right to issue educational documents of the state model to him.

According to the law, higher education organizations have the right to academic freedom, self-management, freedom of research and teaching. Official representatives of universities are taking appropriate measures to ensure that students can study under favorable conditions. A student never wastes his free time. In order to meaningfully organize students' free time, various intellectual games, various regional events are being organized by the youth union of universities. In order for the students to get a good education, there are almost every professor who does not give the student a qualified education. Wide opportunities are also created for students' scientific research. Through such research, many students become the owners of the President's degree, Alisher Navoi, Behbudi and other famous degrees through their work.

Another effective work carried out in the field of education in our country is to ensure the legal provision of the field of education and to show its results, which was adopted in this system on May 19, 2020. The importance of the law has shown the high effectiveness of our country's perspective in the field of education. The main goal of the law is to prepare personnel who can meet the requirements of the time in our country and to further improve their knowledge level based on world experience. opened the door to opportunities. Also, the type of education was mentioned in this law. In particular, in-service education (full-time), in-service education (External,

evening, distance), dual education, family education and independent education , goals and tasks such as education and training of adults, inclusive education, external education, training of personnel in the field of defense, security and law enforcement activities were defined.

One of the main success factors of any organization is the quality of its results. One of the effective methods of ensuring the quality of education is the use of international quality management standards that regulate various aspects of the organization's activities, along with accreditation. A similar approach is used in many foreign universities. Achieving the required quality level that meets the requirements of all interested parties is the result of the operation of a quality management system created, implemented and certified by a third party.

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